

MAHARAJ KUMARI BINODINI DEVI
(1922-2011)

Maharaj Kumari Binodini Devi is the key renaissance figure of modern, contemporary Manipuri culture.

A Manipuri writer who bridged the two worlds of ancient royalty and modern life, M.K. Binodini Devi was born as a princess into a palace life. Yet she transcended the constraints of royalty to live to the full the life of an enlightened commoner and emerged as the iconic pioneer in the evolution of Manipuri modernism.

M.K. Binodini Devi brought a deep humanism and a sense of beauty and esthetics to all her work. She made her name in the wider world as a novelist and a writer of short stories, essays, plays and screenplays of award-winning films, lyrics, poems and ballet scripts. But her work spread beyond literature and film, theater, and dance to sculpture, environmentalism, women's issues, youth, social activism and electoral politics. Her work garnered accolades beyond Manipur on the national stage and in the international arena.

Maharaja Sir Churachand Singh and Maharani Dhamanjuri Devi.

CONNECTING ROYALTY AND MODERNITY

Also known as Sana Wangol, M. K. Binodini Devi was born on February 6, 1922, the youngest of the five daughters of Maharaja Sir Churachand Singh, KSCI, CBE, and Maharani Dhanamanjuri Devi of Manipur. As the first child born after the coronation of Maharaja Churachand, M.K. Binodini Devi held a pre-eminent status among all the children of the royal household.

She was the first female graduate of Manipur. Her education was the result of being the daughter of Manipur's first Western-educated monarch of Manipur and his queen, Maharani Dhanamanjuri, who assigned her English companion, Mrs. E. M. Jolly, as her daughter's first English teacher. M. K. Binodini Devi got her formal English education at Pine Mount School and St Mary's College, Shillong; became fluent in Bengali at Vidyasagar College, West Bengal; and was the first Manipuri woman to study art at Tagore's Viswa Bharati University in Santiniketan.

THE PRINCESS WRITER

M. K. Binodini Devi is that rare writer in the world who comes from the innermost circle of royalty to make a mark in literature. It was in this world that she had unparalleled and privileged access to that she turned her literary imagination to in her celebrated and Sahitya Akademi Award-winning novel *Boro Saheb Ongbi Sanatombi* (1979). The British period in Manipur, coeval with her life as a princess, was fondly captured in a series of essays called *The Last Saheb* and an essay on World War 2 from the Manipuri point of view called *Yengkhom*

Ongbi Hemabati. Known for her horsemanship as a young woman, she wove in interviews to write 24 half-hour radio programs on the Manipur's equestrian culture as she knew it from her life in the palace, commissioned and broadcast by All India Radio. But it was in her last book, *Maharaj Churachandgi Imung* (2009) that her personal experience of Manipuri court life, from family to politics, offered a unique perspective that may never be captured again.

THE PEOPLE'S WRITER

As a writer with leftist leanings, M.K. Binodini Devi was close to the Communist leader Hijam Irabot, a cousin by marriage. She was essentially a writer of the people, a princess brought up in traditional court life who became a voice for the common man.

The vast majority of her literature is about the lives of common people and of the ordinary Manipuri. There is little hint, besides the grace and elegance of her prose, of her privileged upbringing in the understanding and empathy for ordinary people that come through in her collection of short stories called *Nung'gairakta Chandramukhi* (1965). She wrote over 50 song lyrics that became popular hits, many of them on patriotic themes such as *Lairabini Hainei Ima Nangbu Mina*, *Sukna Mamla Guhaa Nungda* and *Nasunglaangini He Imaa*, which became the anthem of the June 18 Uprising of 2001. Her

15 radio plays, like *Imagi Ningthem* which later was made into the internationally acclaimed film by Aribam Syam Sharma, and the plays in her collection *Asangba Nongjabi* (1966), are among the most loved of All India Radio's broadcasts.

THE WRITER AS CULTURAL RENAISSANCE FIGURE

Maharaj Kumari Binodini Devi's home with its open rehearsal *sangoi* in Yaiskul Police Lane, built on the homestead of her mother Maharani Dhanamanjuri Devi, was Manipur's artists' salon for over four decades. It was in this gathering place, where artists came and went freely, that she co-founded Roop Raag, the seminal and influential arts group of post-War Manipur in 1960, and LEIKOL, the noted women's writers' circle .

Here, Aribam Syam Sharma set her lyrics to music, and Nongmaithem Pahari, Aheibam Buddhachandra and Chongtham (née Ayekpam) Kamala brought them to life as some of Manipur's best-loved modern music. Arambam Samarendra rehearsed in a Manipuri Macbeth and mounted his celebrated play *Dashaa* in her *sangoi*. It was here that Ratan Thiyam set up *Andha Yug*, his very first theater production, featuring Yengkhom Roma in the lead. Here, scenes of the films *Lamja Parsuram*, *Olangthagee Wangmadasoo* and *Asangba Nongjabi* were shot. The international award winning *Imagi Ningthem* was edited and dubbed in this home. Ima Kumar Maibi honed the dancing skills of Ima Dhani Maibi and 13 other maibis for the classic film *Ishanou*.

M.K. Binodini Devi on the esraj; with (R-L) Kakchingtabam Gourahari Sharma, Ayekpam Kamala, Aribam Syam Sharma.

Fellow writers like Laisram Samarendra, Lamabam Virmani, Hijam Guno, Khaidem Pramodini, Maibam Haricharan and Ningthoukhongjam Khelchandra dropped in regularly. Writers of LEIKOL came to work with her to anthologize

women's writing on love in *Nachom*. Young artists came to visit their Imasi, royal mother in Meiteilon. The scholars among them came to interview her for their dissertations. National luminaries like Badal Sircar, Naseeruddin Shah and Amol Palekar, came to interact with their Manipuri counterparts. And in the center of it all was M.K. Binodini Devi.

THE WRITER AS SOCIAL ACTIVIST

In her writing and in her arts and social activism, M. K. Binodini Devi is recognized as a pioneer of a non-doctrinaire thinking in Manipur that borrows little from conventional modernism and is rooted deeply in Manipur's own traditions. Her works are notable for their strong, unconventional female characters and young women authors especially look to M. K. Binodini Devi, whom they call *Imasi* or Royal Mother, as a role model. She was the President and Founder of *Leikol*, the literary organization of women writers in Manipur.

M.K. Binodini Devi was a writer whose literature was not just popularized by the people who read her books. A major active presence in the social sphere, she wrote prolifically in the daily newspapers of Manipur. Even her memoir essays on her elevated life in the palace, later collected and published as *Maharaj Churachandgi Imung*, made their first appearance in the daily newspaper *Poknapham* between 2002 and 2007. These essays and others like *The Last Saheb*, about an Anglophone cousin, *Yaikul Yai*, a series of portraits of colorful characters in her neighborhood, and her essays on her international travels, later published as *O Mexico!* (2004) were avidly read by the public when they were serialized in the dailies.

M.K. Binodini Devi with Chongtham Kamala and assistant B.Tarunkumari, 2007.

M. K. Binodini Devi never ceased to write articles and numberless letters to the editors on contemporary events around her, from crimes against women and ransom kidnappings to the state of local rivers.

Few know that she had close personal relationships with the Governors and Chief Ministers and other ministers of the state and often made personal phone calls or wrote private letters to them on issues she felt needed addressing but were too delicate to be aired publicly.

Her concerns and interests went beyond her own Meitei community. She contributes articles to publications of the Nepali Sahitya Parishad of Manipur. Her essays on the Kabui Nagas of her father's court, boldly broke the flow of her elegant prose to list all the names of the musicians of Keisamthong and Moirangkhom *khuls* lest they should be forgotten by future generations.

She has also held elected office as was a Member of the Legislative Assembly in Manipur and founded micro-financing for women in Manipur with the formation of Manipur's first women's cooperative bank in 1973.

As the first Secretary of the Jawaharlal Nehru Manipur Dance Academy, M.K. Binodini Devi pioneered the incorporation of the Manipuri martial arts called Thang-Ta into the canon of classical Manipuri Dance and drew traditional *maibis* into its teaching faculty.

During her time there, she wrote the environmental ballet script for the modern ballet *Thoibi* (1972). This environmental ballet was an elegy to the brow-antlered deer, the *sangai*, whose endangered state and importance she brought to the attention of the people of Manipur, igniting environmental awareness in Manipur, with *Thoibidu Warouhou'ido* (1972). Her environmentalism often took on an active aspect as with *The Nong'goubi Project*, a series of community actions taken in 2002 to clean up the Nambul River.

NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL PROMINENCE

Although M. K. Binodini Devi is known best for her writing, she was also an accomplished sculptor, having been an art student at Tagore's Santiniketan. There, she became the muse of the Indian sculptor and painter Ramkinkar Vaij.

Binodini, oil portrait by Ramkinkar Vaij.

Portraits and sculptures of her by Vaij are in the Gallery of Modern Art in New Delhi and were recently shown in New Delhi, Mumbai and Bangalore. Their relationship was fictionalized in *Dekhi Nai Phire* (unfinished) by the late celebrated Bengali novelist Samaresh Basu, with illustrations by Bikash Bhattacharjee, another contemporary Bengali painter. She has also translated into Manipuri the works of Bengali writers such as Rabindranath Tagore, Shankar and Badal Sircar.

Many national luminaries in the arts such as actor Naseeruddin Shah, actor-director Amol Palekar, playwright Badal Sircar, novelist Mulk Raj Anand, writer Samaresh Basu, director Ketan Mehta, dancers Maya Rao and Sonal Man Singh, and cultural scholar Kapila Vatsyayana made it a point to visit her in her home in Yaiskul. She helped establish Manipuri Dance in Kolkata by mentoring the Sangeet Natak Award winning choreographer Priti Patel.

Internationally, M. K. Binodini Devi took the first all-Manipuri dance troupe on a tour of Latin America, North America and Europe in 1976, resulting in her collection of travel essays called *O Mexico! Lamkoi Wari* (2004). But it is her work in film that of her nine feature films and four documentaries, her collaborations with director Aribam Syam Sharma that M.K. Binodini Devi had the most international impact. Their film *Imagi Ningthem* (My Son, My Precious) received the Grand Prix at the 1981 Festival des 3 Continents at Nantes; their documentary *Sangai, Dancing Deer of Manipur* received the British Film Institute Outstanding Film of the Year Award for 1989; and their feature film *Ishanou* (The Chosen One) was an *Un Certain Regard* selection at the Cannes Film Festival in 1991. Their films have garnered international acclaim at other international venues such as the Museum of Modern Art and Lincoln Center in New York. A

program of a selection of the films they made together was screened at the Brooklyn Academy of Music in New York in 2000.

M. K. Binodini Devi was honored with the Sahitya Akademi Award in 1979 for her novel *Boro Saheb Ongbi Sanatombi*. The Sahitya Akademi also commissioned *Binodini: A Writer's Life* (2001), a documentary film on her literary career, directed by Aribam Syam Sharma. In 2007, the Sahitya Akademi selected her for their Eminent Senior Writer Award. Other awards include the Jamini Sunder Guha Gold Medal in 1966 by the Manipuri Sahitya Parishad for *Nung'gairakta Chandramukhi*, her collection of stories; and the 2002 Kamal Kumari Foundation Award for Culture.

In 1976 she was awarded the Padma Shri (India's national honors list) by the President of India for her contribution to music, drama, dance, film and literature. She subsequently returned the award in 2001 in protest to plans to alter Manipur's historical boundaries.

But the awards that M.K. Binodini Devi loved the most was that her stories like *Charik Pareng* and *Thoibidu Warouhou'ido*, and her novel *Boro Saheb Ongbi Sanatombi*, are taught to young people in Manipur's schools and colleges today.

BINODINI: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

Binodini

- ❖ *Nung'gairakta Chandramukhi* (Chrysanthemum Among the Rocks, 1965), short stories
- ❖ *Asangba Nongjaabi* (Crimson Rainclouds, 1966), plays
- ❖ *Boro Saheb Ongbi Sanatombi* (The Princess and the Political Agent, 1979), novel
- ❖ *Amasung Indrajit* (And Indrajit, 1990), translation of the Bengali play by Badal Sircar
- ❖ *Mexico! Lamkoi Wari* (2004), travel writing about Mexico, the US and Europe
- ❖ *Maharaj Churachandgi Imung* (The Maharaja's Household, memoir essays, 2009)
- ❖ *Isei Binodinigi* (Songs of Binodini, ed.: Aribam Syam Sharma, Chongtham Kamala; Imasi Foundation, 2014)

FILM SCRIPTS (IN MANIPURI)

- ❖ *Olangthagee Wangmadasoo* (feature film, original screenplay, 1980)
- ❖ *Imagi Ningthem* (feature film, 1981)
- ❖ *Paokhum Ama* (feature film, original screenplay, 1983)
- ❖ *Sangai, the Dancing Deer of Manipur* (documentary, 1988),

- ❖ *Ishanou* (feature film, original screenplay, 1990)
- ❖ *Mayopheegee Macha* (feature film, 1994)
- ❖ *Orchids of Manipur* (documentary, 1994)
- ❖ *Sanabi* (feature film, 1995)
- ❖ *La* (documentary, 1997),
- ❖ *Thengmallabara Radha-manbi* (feature film, 1999)
- ❖ *Asangba Nongjaabi* (television feature film, 2003)
- ❖ *Ngahaak Lambida* (short feature, 2006)
- ❖ *Nangna Kappa Pakchade* (feature, 2013)

Bio-documentary

Binodini: A Writer's Life; Aribam Syam Sharma. Producer: Sahitya Akademi, India, 2001, 45 min. Manipuri with English subtitles.

RADIO PLAYS

- ❖ *Baasi Marol Chumdaba*
- ❖ *Imagi Ningthem*
- ❖ *Imphal Kaba*
- ❖ *Jahaanara or Ketaabgi Segaikhraba Lamai*
- ❖ *Kanaana Keithel Kaabini?*
- ❖ *Kaorabara Raas Saannabagi Ahingdo*
- ❖ *Nandini*
- ❖ *Nangna Kappa Pakchade*
- ❖ *Ngaikho, Hingminakhisi*
- ❖ *Sendrembi Cheishra*
- ❖ *Shilpi, later Asangba Nongjaabi*
- ❖ *Thengmallabara Radhamanbi*

Adapted:

- ❖ *Ahing Amagi Wari* (based on a story by Haobam Satyabati)
- ❖ *Charaangnaraba Nung* (Rabindranath Tagore's *Hungry Stones*)
- ❖ *Nongphaadok Laakpada* (based on Lamabam Biramani's *Atithi*)

BALLET SCRIPTS (IN MANIPURI)

- ❖ *Kong Hangoi* (children's ballet, 1971)
- ❖ *Thoibi* (wildlife ballet, 1972)
- ❖ *Keibul Lamjao* (wildlife ballet, 1984)
- ❖ *Loktak Isei* (ecology ballet, 1991)

TRANSLATIONS BY BINODINI

- ❖ *Amasung Indrajit* (*Evam Indrajit*, Badal Sircar)
- ❖ *Solution X* (Badal Sircar)
- ❖ *Sakhangdaba Kayani* (*Koto Ajanare*, Shankar)
- ❖ *Charangnaraba Nung* (*Khudito Pashan*, Rabindranath Tagore)
- ❖ *Karna Kunti Sangbad* (Rabindranath Tagore)
- ❖ *28 Rabindra Sangeet* (Rabindranath Tagore)

SELECTED TRANSLATIONS OF BINODINI INTO ENGLISH

- ❖ *My Son, My Precious* (*Imagi Ningthem*). Cinewave, Calcutta 1981
- ❖ *One Answer* (*Paokhum Ama*). Cinewave, Calcutta 1984
- ❖ *My Little Friend* (*Imphal Turelgi Itaamacha*). Sahitya Akademi anthology. New Delhi 2005

- ❖ *A String of Beads (Chaarik Pareng, in The Grasshopper and Other Stories)*
Cambridge University Press, New Delhi 2011
- ❖ *Crimson Rainclouds (Asangba Nongjaabi)*. Thema Books, Calcutta 2012
- ❖ *The Maharaja's Household (Maharaj Churachandgi Imung)*. Forthcoming,
Zubaan Books, 2015

AWARDS

- ❖ *Nung'gairakta Chandramukhi, Jamini Sunder Guha Gold Medal, 1966*
- ❖ *Padma Shri, 1976, returned 2001*
- ❖ *Boro Saaheb Ongbi Sanatombi, Sahitya Akademi Award, 1979*
- ❖ *Kamal Kumari National Award for Culture, 2002*
- ❖ *Eminent Senior Writer Award, Sahitya Akademi, 2007*
- ❖ *Lifetime Achievement Award, Manipur State Kala Akademi, 2011*
(posthumous)

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TRUSTEES

Thoudam Debendra Singh
Aribam Syam Sharma
Ratan Thiyam
Dr. Moirangthem Nara Singh
Prof. Gangmumei Kamei
Dr. R.K. Nimai Singh
Chongtham Kamala Devi
Yengkhom Roma
Priti Patel
Saratchand Thiyam
Huidrom Anuradha Devi
Dr. Sheelaramani Chungkham
L. Gourachandra Sharma
Mayanglambam Mangangsana
Salam Rajesh

L. Somi Roy
Founder, Managing Trustee

Ngangom Tejkumar, Esq.
Legal Counsel

The Imasi Foundation
Kombirei House
Hijigang Lane
Palace Compound
Imphal, 795001
Manipur

IMASI: The Maharaj Kumari Binodini Devi Foundation recognizes that the literary and artistic legacy of M. K. Binodini is an integral and important part of the cultural legacy of Manipur. Her sense of, commitment to, and expression of aesthetics and humanism form the guiding spirit in pursuing the objectives of IMASI.

The objective of IMASI is to preserve, protect, promote and develop the artistic, intellectual and cultural legacy of M.K. Binodini Devi. It will support and develop initiatives in Manipur's culture: its literature, performing arts, history, religious heritage, environment, internationalism, women, and youth.

+91-87-94-37-92-02
1goalprojects@gmail.com

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Facebook: Imasi: The Maharaj Kumari Binodini Devi Foundation